

RNA therapies hold great promise for treating cancer. High-throughput screening techniques have facilitated the development of RNA treatments

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Abstract- High throughput screening techniques have facilitated the creation of RNA treatments, and these findings have been accompanied by unique modifications of RNA structures to increase stability and minimize toxicity, as well as innovative delivery systems such as LNPs. "undruggable" targets, "swiftly construct vaccinations," and to provide therapeutic approaches that can be tailored to individual patients Like the genetic code, RNA therapies hold great promise.

At the same time, our hospital launched a specialized RNA Therapeutics program that assists both our internal scientists and external academic groups or small firms aiming to apply their fundamental research discoveries to innovative treatments. mRNA is primarily stable because of our primary study in sequencing and structure. For synthesis, purification, and validation of RNA constructs, we have a contemporary GMP program with clean rooms. Our company collaborates with Nanomedicine to build LNP structures that transport mRNA constructs locally and systemically. We have an opportunity to hire and integrate first-in-man clinical trials unit, as well as a big hospital system with a clinical research infrastructure that enables industry-sponsored Phase 2 and 3 clinical trials. Additionally, we have a large-scale mRNA construction industrial sponsor for Phases 2, 3, and commercialization. Essentially, we've put up a production line for universities and small firms interested in turning their mRNA creations into revolutionary medications. One hospital, one point of entry to ensure that RNA-based drugs are created and translated into the clinic efficiently. Many tiny firms with fresh concepts for disruptive mRNA therapeutics cannot reach the clinic without new translational capabilities. We think we are the only academic organization with the infrastructure to help small academic groups and biotech enterprises, and we want to aid both internal and external translational activities in the coming years.

I. INTRODUCTION

Background information

Due to its participation in the first two vaccines for the coronavirus illness 2019 virus, the field of RNA therapeutics has lately gained widespread interest. This, however, is only one illustration of the therapeutic revolution that is currently taking place. The potential of RNA stems from the fact that it is basically biological software that can be quickly developed and created, with a wide range of applications based on modification of the expression or activity of any therapeutically important protein. As seen by continuing clinical development of vaccines for infectious illness and cancer, enzyme replacement, and cell therapy modification, RNA-based treatments have a wide range of uses. There are also no limits on how it may be used to treat cardiovascular illnesses (1). New advancements in nucleic acid therapy production, design, and delivery systems have lately enabled the translation of RNA biology into treatments.

II. MECHANISMS OF ACTION OF RNA

The temporary blueprints of genes contained in genomic DNA are known as mRNAs (2). The cell's translational machinery acts on the mRNA transcripts to produce the encoded proteins (3,4). Exogenous mRNA can be introduced into the cell by RNA-based therapies (3,5), while endogenous mRNA can be inhibited using RNA-based therapies (6,7).

Antisense oligonucleotides (ASO), small interfering RNAs (siRNA), and microRNAs are all effective ways to silence endogenous mRNA (miRNA). Although all of these RNAs bind to complementary regions on target mRNA and prevent it from being translated, the molecular processes through which they interfere with endogenous mRNA differ. Therapeutic ASOs are single-stranded nucleic acids that form a duplex with target mRNA and engage RNase H to hydrolyze it. PremRNA processing and mRNA translation can be sterically blocked by the

RNA/ASO duplex (8–10). Endogenous siRNA and miRNA, on the other hand, are noncoding RNA duplexes that must be processed by cell machinery and interact with the RNA-induced silencing complex, which cleaves or represses mRNA translation (11–15). Because siRNA is completely complementary to the target transcript, it affects just one gene's expression (very specific), but miRNA is only partially complementary and can influence numerous genes. Agomirs and antagomirs are second-generation short RNAs that are very stable in vivo when used to modulate RNA expression. Agomirs are chemically modified double-strand miRNA mimics containing phosphorothioates at the 5' and 3' ends, a cholesterol group at the 3' end, and a nucleotide 2'-methoxy alteration along the length of the construct. Agomirs silence their target mRNA by acting like mature endogenous miRNA. Antagomirs have a similar structure to antagomirs, but they limit the action of target miRNAs on a permanent basis. Stability (usage of 2'-OME and phosphorothioate modifications) and delivery (e.g., cholesterol conjugation to promote dispersion and cell permeability) have been improved as a result of these advances in nucleic acid therapeutic design (16).

In certain circumstances, mRNA-silencing strategies are better to traditional pharmacotherapies because they may be engineered to suppress the translation of mRNA encoding any protein. They can specifically change the expression of proteins that would normally be difficult to impact with small molecules, such as proteins with an inaccessible shape or nonenzymatic activity (17). mRNA therapies, on the other hand, provide an exogenous message that is delivered into the cell to produce a therapeutic protein, such as to replace a faulty protein (gene replacement therapy) or to introduce transcripts that are not naturally present in the cell (antigens for vaccination, chimeric antigen receptors for cell therapy).

Therapy with mRNA often uses RNA constructs with thousands of nucleotides, as opposed to silence of endogenous mRNA, which often needs constructions in the tens of nucleotides range, resulting in significant disparities in the synthesis of these two classes of molecules. mRNA therapies, on the other hand, may be tailored to encode almost any protein or antigen, allowing them to address hitherto unreachable sites. RNA sequences may be easily changed, allowing mRNA treatment to be tailored to the individual. Because mRNA is translated into protein in the cytoplasm rather than the nucleus, it may be more practicable and safe than DNA-based gene therapy (plasmids, viral vectors), which must reach the nucleus and risk integrating into the host genome (18).

Synthetic mRNA's therapeutic impact was first proven in 1992, when mRNA encoding vasopressin was injected into the hypothalamus of rats with central diabetes insipidus and the condition was transiently reversed (19). Early attempts to use RNA as a drug were challenged by its intrinsic ability to activate innate immune signaling and cause inflammation and apoptosis (22,23), despite the fact that manufacturing of RNA therapeutics is relatively simple and involves either chemical synthesis (ASOs, siRNA, miRNA) (20) or enzymatic transcription in vitro (IVT) from the DNA template (mRNA) (21). This problem was solved by synthesizing a number of chemically modified nucleotides and combining them with an RNA molecule (24). Furthermore, several byproducts produced during IVT, such as double-stranded RNA, have been shown to contribute to inflammatory activation. This discovery sparked the development of new purification techniques that, when combined with chemical changes, significantly lowered RNA toxicity (25). Furthermore, innovations in RNA design have aided in improving RNA stability and translatability by optimizing sequence (both untranslated sections and open reading frames) (26–28). A newly suggested method for circularizing mRNA decreases RNA fragility by making it resistant to RNA exonucleases, which are ubiquitously present (29,30). In addition, certain lyophilization techniques were investigated in order to extend the shelf life of RNA and make transit and storage easier (31,32). In the recent decade, all of the aforementioned advancements have rendered mRNA clinically promising. However, for RNA-based cardiovascular therapies, delivery remains a challenge that demands specific attention.

III. DELIVERY OF RNA THERAPEUTICS IN THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM

Preclinical investigations have demonstrated proof-of-concept for the use of adeno-associated virus serotype 9, which selectively distributes miRNA to cardiac myocytes, for example to boost myocyte proliferation following a myocardial infarction (33). Viral vectors, on the other hand, have intrinsic flaws, such as an immunological response to the vector. Due to their good safety profile, minimal immunogenicity, and simplicity of fabrication, lipid nanoparticles (LNPs) have begun to supplant viral vectors as the preferred delivery strategy for RNA-based therapeutics (34). To be sure, LNPs aren't completely harmless, as seen by the uncommon allergic responses to RNA vaccinations that have been linked to the polyethylene glycol component of the LNPs (35).

Khan et al. used a polymeric nanoparticle to control abnormal endothelium expression of Tie2 siRNA supplied systemically to nonhuman monkeys as an example of nonviral delivery. With low damage, this method successfully lowered Tie2 expression in the heart, lungs, retina, and kidney (36). In this scenario, however, the siRNA should be administered to both normal and sick endothelium. LNP systems have recently advanced to the point where they may target active endothelium, such as that seen above atherosclerotic plaques (37,38).

Aside from targeted drug eluting stent administration (39,40), effective delivery techniques have focused on utilizing variations in blood flow patterns within the vasculature and endothelial changes to target sick tissue. In this aspect, blood flow in the arterial tree is typically laminar, with shear stress ranging from 10 to 20 dynes/cm². Endothelial cells respond to shear stress via mechanoreceptors, flow-activated ion channels, and associated proteins like Yes-associated protein and its paralog transcription activator with PDZ binding motif (Tafazzin), which regulate cell structure and functions like nitric oxide synthase and vascular endothelial growth factor receptor expression and activity (41,42).

Disturbed flow generates a low oscillatory shear stress on the endothelium at bends, branches, and bifurcations, as well as at sites of vascular disease, altering signaling pathways such as BMP–TGF, WNT, Notch, HIF1, TWIST1, and NFκB, contributing to the expression of adhesion molecules such as intercellular adhesion molecule-1, E-selectin, and vascular cell adhesion molecule (These alterations not only continue the cycle of vascular inflammation, but they also pave the way for therapies to be targeted particularly to these locations.

The creation of leukocyte-based biomimetic nanoparticles is one technique that takes advantage of sick vasculature' endothelial adhesiveness (i.e., leukosomes). The LNP is used to construct leukosomes by incorporating membrane proteins from leukocytes. In animal studies, the leukosomes target activated endothelium and accumulate more efficiently in atherosclerotic and tumor arteries (38). Leukosomes were created utilizing membrane proteins isolated from activated J774 macrophages and loaded with rapamycin in a landmark research (37). Leukosomes localized to the damaged aorta in Apo E/ animals to a much larger extent than ordinary LNPs. Furthermore, in mice treated with rapamycin using leukosomes, macrophage proliferation was reduced to a greater extent, which was correlated with a greater decrease in levels of MCP-1 and IL-1b in the aortic wall, as well as reduced aortic matrix metalloproteinases activity, when compared to mice treated with standard LNP delivery. The leuko-rapa platform was shown to reduce macrophage proliferation inside the aorta following a short (7-day) dosage schedule with a low toxicity profile in this proof-of-concept study (37). This therapy might be a potential intervention for the acute stabilization of late-stage plaques, and though the cargo load in this work was rapamycin, the formulation may be altered to encapsulate RNA as an LNP.

Krohn-Grimberghe et al. employed LNPs that concentrate exclusively within the bone marrow to deliver siRNA suppressing MCP1 rather than directly targeting inflamed vasculature. They used this technology to reduce leukocyte release from the hematopoietic niche and promote healing after infarction in a rat model while reducing heart failure (45). As a result, instead of directly targeting the heart or blood arteries, other organs might be used to treat cardiovascular illness. Current RNA therapeutics for cardiovascular disease are mostly directed towards the liver, taking use of the ability of untargeted LNPs to be taken up by the reticuloendothelial system in the liver and spleen, as explained below.

As indicated by recent techniques employing nanoparticles that localize to active endothelium, the future of RNA treatments for cardiovascular disease is certainly heading in the direction of tailored medicines. Proof-of-concept has been demonstrated for a biomimetic method that mimics adhesion and transmigration by functionalizing the LNP with membrane proteins. More research into analogous biomimetic ways to mimic leukocyte adhesion to develop the second generation of RNA-LNPs for cardiovascular disease is anticipated to result from the findings of these investigations.

IV. CLINICAL TRIALS OF RNA THERAPEUTICS ARE CURRENTLY IN PROGRESS.

Despite considerable improvements in treatment choices, cardiovascular disease is still the leading cause of mortality in the United States, accounting for 17.8 million deaths globally (46). While there are just a few clinical trials for RNA therapies for cardiovascular illnesses, rising research and funding in this field ensures that there will be more in the future.

Mipomersen, a second-generation phosphorothioate ASO that targets mRNA expressing apolipoprotein B-100, was one of the first nucleic acid treatments for cardiovascular disease. Initially, the medication was approved to treat homozygous familial hypercholesterolemia. Mipomersen decreased total LDL levels while raising total reactive C-protein levels (48). Despite these findings, the European Medicines Agency removed Mipomersen from clinical use in Europe in 2013 due to serious liver damage (49,50). Later generations of ASOs have been chemically changed to have lower toxicity as a result of the findings. After either a 20 mg weekly injection or a 60 mg injection every four weeks, more than 90% of patients in a recent Phase II study using TQJ230 (AKCEA-APO(a)-LRx), an ASO targeting lipoprotein(a) mRNA, reached lipoprotein(a) concentrations below 50 mg/dl (51). Volanesorsen is another ASO that has made it to clinical trials. This ASO may be administered subcutaneously and works by binding to and stimulating the breakdown of APOC3 mRNA. Volanesorsen reduced Apoc-II (80 percent) and triglycerides (71 percent) in a Phase II research, while increasing HDL-cholesterol levels (46 percent) (52). Initial negative findings with ASOs haven't halted research, and later variants have been chemically changed to lessen toxicity (53).

Targeting mRNA encoding the enzyme proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 9 (PCSK9), which is mostly generated in the liver, is another way to decrease cholesterol (54–56). PCSK9 binds to the LDL receptor (LDL-R) on the surface of hepatocytes, causing LDL-R to be degraded and hence plasma LDL-cholesterol levels to rise. With a covalently bonded triantennary N-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc) ligand, Inclisiran is a synthetic, chemically modified siRNA targeting PCSK9 mRNA. After a twice-annual subcutaneous injection, Inclisiran met all primary and secondary endpoints in three Phase III trials, had a favorable safety profile, and matched the LDL-lowering efficiency of antibody-based PCSK9 inhibitors alirocumab (Praluent; Regeneron/Sanofi) and evolocumab (Repatha; Amgen, Thousand Oaks, California, USA) (51,57,58). In individuals with severe hypercholesterolemia who are taking the highest dosage of antilipid therapy (e.g., statins), inclisiran lowers LDL cholesterol by 40–50%. The European Commission has authorized inclisiran for the treatment of drug-resistant hypercholesterolemia in adults based on these trials.

Beyond medications that block endogenous mRNA, the mRNA encoding vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF)-A mRNA is the first and only cardiovascular-related mRNA medication to enter clinical trials (Moderna, Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA). Intradermal delivery of VEGF-A mRNA boosted local VEGF-A protein expression (as measured by cutaneous microdialysis) and skin blood flow in men with type 2

diabetes in a Phase I research (59). Based on these findings, the EPICCURE Phase 2a clinical study will see if this mRNA therapy may repair ischemic but viable myocardium areas in patients with coronary artery disease as measured by ejection fraction (60). This is a multicenter, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial in patients receiving coronary artery bypass surgery who have moderately reduced systolic function. Patients are randomized to receive epicardial injections of 0, 3, or 30 mg of VEGF A mRNA in a citrate buffer (dosage split into 30 injections delivered into the ischemic myocardium, as preoperatively mapped by PET imaging).

If this systematic effort succeeds, it will give proof that injecting mRNA directly into an ischemic tissue may enhance perfusion and function. Many previous angiogenic gene treatments have failed, possibly due to a lack of understanding about the proper dose, duration, and administration of the angiogenic agents (61-331).

V. FINAL REMARKS

High throughput screening techniques to find target genes and sequences have aided the growth of RNA therapeutics (62,63), and these discoveries have been complemented by novel modifications of RNA constructs to improve stability and reduce toxicity, as well as improved delivery methods such as LNPs (64). The potential of RNA therapies is enabled by a significant convergence of advancements, which includes the potential to develop novel medications for "undruggable" targets, swiftly build vaccines against infectious illnesses that underpin pandemics, and genuinely customize treatments. RNA treatments have as much potential as the genetic code on which they are founded.

Recognizing the importance of this new therapeutic arena, we have created a fully integrated RNA Therapeutics program at our hospital that supports both our internal scientists and external academic groups or small businesses looking to translate their basic research findings into transformative therapies. We do basic research on the sequence and structure of mRNA, which underpins its stability and translation. For the synthesis, purification, and validation of RNA constructs, we have a current good manufacturing practice program with clean rooms. We collaborate with our Nanomedicine colleagues to develop LNP structures that can deliver mRNA constructs locally and systemically. A Comparative Medicine Program with expertise in good laboratory practice preclinical studies; a first-in-man clinical trials unit for Phase 1 and 2a studies; and a large hospital system with a clinical research infrastructure that supports industry-sponsored Phase 2 and 3 clinical trials are all available to us. We also have an industrial sponsor for large-scale mRNA construct manufacture for Phases 2, 3, and commercialization. In essence, we've set up a production line for university research groups and small businesses looking to turn their mRNA constructions into transformational medicines. Our hospital-based RNA therapies initiative offers a single point of entry with counseling to guarantee that RNA-based medications are developed and translated smoothly into the clinic. Many small organizations with new concepts for disruptive mRNA treatments lack essential translational abilities to reach the clinic, necessitating the creation of such a program. We believe we are the only academic group with the infrastructure to completely support small academic groups and biotech firms, and we intend to assist both internal and external translational initiatives in the next years to realize the immense potential of RNA therapies.

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